

D6.1 - Report on Use Case definition, demonstration setup and validation plan

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
OTA	Over the air update
MASA	Modena Automotive Smart Area

Executive Summary

The dAIEDGE Project targets three industrial-grade applications as use-cases, specifically one within the smart city domain (High-performance low-power edge&fog technologies for smart cities), one in the space domain (AI on the edge for satellite image processing) and finally one in the logistics domain (Drone assisted warehouse security monitoring & inspection). This deliverable outlines the application requirements and the defined performance metrics for the three use cases, each aligned with its respective domain.

Partner Hipert will be responsible for implementing the smart city use case, DLR will handle the space use case, and VERSES will be responsible for the logistics use case.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Objectives

This report is the first of a series of deliverables associated to Work Package 6:

D6.1 – Report on Use Case definition, demonstration setup and validation plan

D6.2 – Report on demonstration implementation

D6.3 – Validation and test report

The objective of this first report is to collect and characterize the requirements of the three use cases addressed in the project. Within this document, we identify a set of requirements for each application, forming the foundation for the demonstration, validation and benchmarking phases.

2. High-performance low-power Edge & FOG technologies for smart cities

2.1. Background

In accordance with projections, [it is anticipated that 68% of the global population will be residing in urban areas](#) by 2050. Consequently, there is an imperative need for enhanced city management, particularly in terms of security and safety measures. Illustrating this ongoing urbanization, in Singapore, [the projected number of police cameras is set to reach 200,000 by 2030](#), playing a significant role in bolstering urban security.

Nevertheless, the effective use of this extensive surveillance network demands efficient monitoring systems. In the 1990s, [Jim Aldridge at the UK Police Scientific and Development Branch \(PSDB\) demonstrated that as more monitors are added to an operator's workstation, detection rates decrease](#). The study illustrated that accuracy in detection drops with the number of screens being monitored as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Table 1: Effect on the accuracy of increasing the number of monitored screens

Number of screens monitored	Accuracy
1	85%
4	74%
6	58%
9	53%

This problem underscores the significance of automated systems in addressing the evolving challenges of urban security. Smart cities play a crucial role in this paradigm shift.

In the context of smart-cities, [Bogota has realized a remarkable 40% improvement in emergency response capabilities attributed to the implementation of smart city systems](#). Other cities around the world are also examples of the trend. This underscores the pivotal role of advanced technologies, such as dAIEdge, in ensuring the efficacy and precision of smart city operations. As cities continue

to evolve and urbanize, the integration of cutting-edge technologies becomes increasingly essential in addressing the complex demands of modern urban living.

The first use case focuses on enhancing the power efficiency and performance of technologies that manage urban mobility and security, leveraging a cutting-edge device developed by Hipert known as **HAura**. This embedded kit, composed of a camera, computing board and software, enables real-time identification, geolocalization and tracking of vehicles, pedestrians and various road users. HAura computes all the data onboard, the metadata produced by the device is seamlessly transmitted to a server. Depending on the municipality or private entity, the server implements different applications to monitor road users and execute smart urban strategies. At the time of writing, HAura is deployed in several Italian cities to enhance public safety and optimize traffic flow, including Modena, Reggio Emilia, and Torino.

This use case aligns with the project's focus on architectural advancements for AI, energy efficiency, contextual computing, computational collaboration, miniaturization and the cloud/edge continuum. In this context, the primary objective of the use case is to improve the power consumption, performance and set of useful actionable outputs provided by HAura's embedded board. The consortium will investigate innovative hardware architectures beyond traditional GPU dependencies to enhance power efficiency and improve the overall performance-to-watt cost ratio.

On the software side, partners will contribute by proposing and implementing cutting-edge neural networks or training approaches tailored to road-user detection, specifically designed to operate on the selected hardware architecture.

2.1.1. Smart-city open innovations

Smart cities can contribute in multiple ways to urban environments, fostering a paradigm shift in how cities function and enhancing the overall quality of life for the society. By leveraging advanced technologies and data-driven solutions, smart cities aim to address diverse challenges and promote sustainable, safe and efficient urban living.

In this line, the integration of advanced technologies brings forth a range of functionalities aimed at enhancing the urban life. Examples of these functionalities include:

Smart infrastructure and sustainability:

- Incorporating intelligent transportation systems, energy-efficient buildings and advanced utility management.
- Prioritizing renewable energy sources, energy-efficient technologies and smart grid systems.

Data-driven governance and citizen engagement:

- Making informed decisions through data analytics regarding urban planning, resource allocation, and public services.
- Promoting active citizen involvement through digital platforms, mobile apps, and social media channels.

Urban mobility solutions and traffic management:

- Offering diverse transportation options such as bike-sharing programs, electric vehicles, and efficient public transportation systems.

- One valuable functionality in a smart city system is intelligent parking detection. Through the deployment of smart-cameras in strategic positions, the system can efficiently monitor parking spaces, providing real-time information to drivers regarding available parking spots.
- Integrating traffic management applications for alleviating congestion, enhancing traffic flow, and reducing travel times.
 - Through real-time monitoring and data analytics, smart cities enable traffic analysis, optimizing the traffic flow, reducing travel times and potentially reducing the fuel consumption.

Safety, security, and emergency response:

- Implementing technologies for comprehensive security, emergency response, and early detection of incidents.
 - Smart cities may feature technologies for comprehensive security and emergency response. This includes the integration of systems for responsive accident detection mechanisms, innovative solutions aimed at enhancing public safety or early detection of fire incidents.
- Deploying advanced surveillance systems, predictive analytics, and emergency response mechanisms for public safety.
 - Implementing V2X technologies the smart-city can communicate with road to alert drivers about vehicles or obstacles in their blind spots. This proactive measure significantly reduces the risk of accidents and enhances overall road safety, fostering a secure environment for both pedestrians and drivers.

While the term Smart Cities encompasses several sectors as shown above, some of them do not necessarily require edge technologies (such as Data-driven governance and citizen engagement). In dAIEDge we will focus on two of the most prominent sectors that can benefit from edge Artificial Intelligence: 1) Safety and Security and 2) Urban mobility and traffic.

2.2. Use case description

MASA (Modena Automotive Smart Area) is a 3km²-wide area of urban territory, adjacent to a transportation hub (train station, bus stops), equipped with cameras, sensors and private communication networks (4G, 5G soon). The area is used as a living experiment and a testing ground for several automotive and smart-communities projects by the local University and companies for the experimentation of vehicles with Cooperative, connected and automated mobility (CCAM) capabilities. To do so, MASA features cameras around the area that 1) capture road images for the detection and tracking of road-users (cars, bikes, pedestrians etc...) and 2) produce geolocalized information (GPS coordinates) of the objects tracked in the world.

MASA administrators are planning to adopt new technologies aimed at enhancing traffic safety, security and privacy. In this context, one of the new features MASA is planning to implement, is to communicate warning alerts to road users such as cars or other smart technologies like VR/AR devices in situations where the vehicle cannot accurately perceive the potential risk of an accident (due to occlusions for instance). Unfortunately, the current HAura deployed version does not offer safe and reliable end-to-end computing guarantees. This implies that the processing time taken by the edge cannot meet safety-related requirements. Furthermore, the current HAura version features a computational board that can be improved in terms of power efficiency, opening the door to propose new architectures that aim to improve the power efficiency and address the

processing time challenges, ensuring safe and reliable end-to-end computing guarantees for deterministic and sustainable traffic management.

Hence, the objective of this use case is to provide reliable edge computing performance and power efficiency in a smart city scenario. Specifically, with this use case dAIEDGE will enable:

1. From WP3 the integration of novel AI-based methods on top of cutting-edge heterogeneous edge devices in the smart city. For instance, extreme edge learning algorithms for continual/lifelong training for the identification of road-users or distributed. This will allow the generation of knowledge based on the use of the data produced by HAura.
2. From WP4 the implementation of services that are efficient and can be used in a generic network infrastructure. These services can support decentralized AI services and will serve as a basis for the demonstration of reliable fog-to-edge computation and communication in the smart city. This eases the interaction of the edge with vehicles or other technologies like VR/AR devices.
3. From WP5 the deployment of high-performance low-power edge devices and methods will bring these technologies closer to a deployment phase in a real smart city environment.

Moreover, the dAIEdge framework will facilitate the effective deployment of AI in human-centric applications. This includes placing specific emphasis on bolstering the adoption of these new technologies in society and enhancing the security of personal data, ultimately contributing to road safety and urban security. We expect that the successful accomplishment of this use case might offer guidelines for the successful deployment of new technologies at high TRL (Technology Readiness Level) in smart cities.

2.2.1. HAura high-level description

The proposed device, named HAura, is an intelligent camera designed for security management and data analysis in Smart Cities and industrial contexts. Specifically, the system processes data from two cameras continuously, with an image transmission frequency of 10Hz, enabling real-time identification of the position and speed of road actors, such as vehicles, pedestrians, and bicycles, in a privacy-sensitive manner. The metadata produced is sent to a server that can implement any application utilizing the produced data to make specific urban mobility decisions. For instance, the municipality of Modena is employing this device to implement smart-road strategies and enhance traffic efficiency. An example of the visualization used by the municipality to make such decisions is depicted in Figure 1. This visualization shows a heat map illustrating the number of road-users and their distribution on the map. Furthermore, it is possible to remotely visualize the status of the network and monitor the status of the computational board.

Figure 1: Example of the municipality user interface

As shown in Figure 2, HAura currently relies on NVIDIA, which poses a limitation since commercial Nvidia SoCs excel in performance but lack in terms of energy efficiency. This limitation hinders the deployment of solutions at high TRL where optimal energy efficiency is crucial. To address this constraint, the dAIEdge consortium will also explore alternative SoC options that balance performance and energy efficiency, ensuring the scalability and viability of HAura in various deployment scenarios with elevated TRL requirements.

Regarding the software aspect, the illustrated pipeline in Figure 2 outlines the process applied to estimate the latitude, longitude, orientation, and estimated speed of road users. This software pipeline relies on the NVIDIA ecosystem (CUDA and tensor cores mainly). Partners will delve into innovative learning approaches aimed at diminishing the computational cost of the existing solution (if feasible) and explore alternative APIs and programming languages that do not necessitate direct dependence on Nvidia technologies.

Figure 2: Diagram of the HAura's hardware, processing pipeline, and data produced

Hipert will open the HAura ecosystem to project partners to enhance the overall solution and introduce new technological advancements in both software and hardware. Specifically, the features of HAura that Hipert will provide to the project partners include:

- **Smart traffic monitoring:** The software implemented by Hipert allows to detect, track and geolocate vehicles, pedestrians, cyclists, and other road actors. Using artificial vision algorithms and machine learning, the framework produces a metadata representation of the traffic condition. The functionalities described above are considered basic features. Other applications are built on top of the main functionalities (i.e., detection, tracking and geolocalization). These applications include vehicle counting, traffic profiling, creating heat maps to identify crowded areas, congestion detection and vehicle classification into different categories.
- **Open interface for third-party applications:** The developed system offers an open interface to enable the development of innovative applications by third parties. In this regard, partners can contribute to implementing any application on top of the smart traffic monitoring platform (for instance parking-space detection leveraging the detection capabilities of HAura). Other innovative third-party applications can be also integrated, such as video surveillance of public spaces.
- **V2X communication in real-time:** The device supports real-time Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication, enabling information exchange between vehicles, road infrastructure and other actors in the urban mobility system. Hipert commits to providing support for leveraging the metadata produced by the cameras within the consortium.
- **Over the Air Update (OTA):** HAura supports over-the-air updates, allowing remote software and camera configuration updates quickly and efficiently, ensuring security and constant feature updates. Hipert will make available the current OTA ecosystem, in this way, project partners will be able to update the software without requiring physical interaction.

2.3. Technical specification

2.3.1. HAura hardware description

HAura is equipped with a robust waterproof case designed to withstand diverse weather conditions. This case hosts essential hardware components, including the computational board, camera, GPS and antennas. This hardware configuration ensures durability and reliability in various environmental scenarios. Figure 3 shows Haura's case and the case that hosts the main hardware components. In particular, the main technical properties of the integrated hardware are:

- **Embedded solution:** The hardware is powered by an NVIDIA embedded solution, featuring an ARM CPU combined with NVIDIA GPU capabilities.
- **Multistream management:** Capable of handling 2 independent streams simultaneously.
- **Supported resolutions:** The system supports a resolution from 640x480 (VGA) to 1920x1080 (1080p), ensuring clear and detailed image capture.
- **Application frequency:** Achieves a smooth operational frequency of 15 FPS for 2 independent streams, enhancing real-time monitoring capabilities.
- **Stream source:** Incorporates 2 cameras as the source for the independent streams, providing comprehensive coverage.

Figure 3: HAura hardware components

HAura employs an integrated sensor set, primarily consisting of built-in cameras designed to capture real-time video data. This sensor configuration has been specifically chosen for detecting and tracking vehicles and pedestrians in an urban domain. The most important properties of the camera and housing hardware are:

- **Camera configuration:** The sensor set comprises two RGB cameras. These cameras offer a wide 120° field of view, ensuring comprehensive coverage of the surveillance area.
- **Sensor mounting:** The sensors are mounted within dedicated cases crafted from PA12 polyamide material.
- **Certifications and protection:** Both the sensors and the housing cases adhere to the highest standards. The sensors have CE certification, ensuring compliance with European safety requirements. Additionally, the dedicated cases have an IP67 protection rating.

The computational board integrated in HAura has undergone changes throughout its design and implementation. The architectures employed have varied, ranging from low-power solutions such as Movidius' Myriad to classic SoCs from NVIDIA (Jetson TX2 and Jetson Nano). One of the most reliable architectures we deployed on HAura is the Jetson NX platform, which provides a good balance in terms of power efficiency and AI performance.

In this context, modern heterogeneous SoCs (hSoC) typically consist of a multi-core CPU host, hardware accelerators, and the associated memory hierarchy. The NVIDIA Jetson Xavier NX, a powerful system-on-module (SoM) designed for edge AI applications, exemplifies this architecture. As shown in Figure 4, the SoC integrates a 6-core NVIDIA Carmel ARM®v8.2 64-bit CPU, featuring a total of 6MB L2 and 4MB L3 cache. Complementing the CPU is a 384-core NVIDIA Volta™ GPU equipped with 48 Tensor Cores, delivering an impressive AI performance of 21 TOPS. The system memory comprises an 8 GB 128-bit LPDDR4x module.

Figure 4: HAura NVIDIA adopted architecture

A more general description of the hardware properties of the whole solution are described in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Table 2: HAura hardware features

Feature	Description
Certifications	CE
Operating Temperature	-25°C to 90°C
IP Protection Level	IP 67
Total Size	418x370x172 mm
Weight	5.45 Kg
Material	Aluminium
Surface Treatment	Powder coating
Horizontal Field of View	120°
Vertical Field of View	25°
Available Interfaces	Ethernet
Power Supply	220V
Typical Power Consumption	20 W

2.3.2. HAura software description

As described above, HAura's proprietary software facilitates real-time object (and people) detection and tracking. The software features a monitoring platform for remote system performance

assessments and seamless over-the-air updates. To gain a better understanding of the current software properties and the starting point of the software provided to the dAIEdge consortium, a detailed list is provided:

- **Communication protocols:** The system employs HTTPS and SSH for secure communication, while metadata communication is facilitated through the MQTT protocol.
- **GPS positioning:** HAura integrates GPS positioning, enriching the system with geospatial information.
- **Network support:** The system supports Wi-Fi in both 2.4GHz and 5GHz spectrums, SIM cards, and Ethernet.
- **Recognized categories:** The software can recognize different categories including pedestrians, cars, bicycles, vans, buses, and motorcyclists (other classes are supported under request).
- **Guaranteed recognition range:** For precise identification, the system guarantees the following recognition ranges: 40 meters for pedestrians, 45 meters for cyclists, and 50 meters for cars.
- **Remote platform monitoring:** The software incorporates a feature for remote monitoring of the platform, allowing continuous assessment of system performance (available computational resources, temperature, etc...).
- **Over-the-Air (OTA) updates:** The system supports fail-safe over-the-air updates with granular control, enabling updates at the level of a single source file, application or even the operating system.
- **Operating system:** Based on Linux with a proprietary distribution, the operating system is optimized for the current system's specific properties.

The system is focused on machine learning and computer vision tasks. The primary input data comprises real-time video streams captured by HAura's cameras, featuring a resolution of 640x480 pixels. This input is processed by Haura software and as output the system generates JSON data. The JSON file includes categorized information represented by numeric IDs (e.g., 0 for a person), latitude, longitude, tracking ID, device ID, and detection timestamp. An example of a generic produced file is shown below. Figure 5 illustrates an example of the visualization of the JSON produced by the software.

```
{
  "camIdx": 0,
  "nObjects": 1,
  "objects": [
    {
      "latitude": 45.06582260131836,
      "longitude": 7.662070274353027,
      "speed": 0.0,
      "orientation": 0,
      "id": 1089,
      "cl": 2
    }
  ]
}
```

```
]
}
```

In compliance with privacy regulations set by Italian authorities, Hipert will grant project partners access to this described output. Partners will contribute to improving the hardware or software integrated into Haura, validating efficiency in terms of computational performance or energy efficiency. For comprehensive assessments, Hipert will provide access to both the JSON output and end-to-end timing results of the neural network and hardware computing this output.

Figure 5. HAura software output. The left side depicts the bounding boxes, while the right side shows the position of the vehicles projected on a Google Maps interface.

2.4. Validation plan

This section outlines the functional, non-functional requirements and KPIs crucial for the comprehensive assessment of the HAura system's performance in the smart city use case.

2.4.1. KPIs

This sub-section outlines essential metrics for evaluating the performance and effectiveness of the system within the smart city context. Each KPI is accompanied by specific objectives, performance indicators and rationale, providing the process framework for assessing the system's performance.

2.4.1.1 KPI-1: Tracking accuracy

- **Objective:** The system shall undergo a rigorous accuracy assessment to ensure precision in recognizing various categories, including pedestrians, cars, bicycles, etc.
- **Performance Indicator:** The detection accuracy shall achieve a minimum Mean Average Precision (MAP) of 0.5:0.95 and an Average Precision (AP50) on the COCO dataset. The system's recognition capabilities must consistently meet or exceed these specified thresholds under diverse operating conditions and environmental scenarios.
- **Rationale:** This requirement is essential to guarantee the system's reliability and effectiveness in identifying and categorizing objects within its operational domain.

2.4.1.2 **KPI-2: Software timing capabilities**

- Objective: The system shall undergo a comprehensive evaluation of its timing capabilities for identifying and tracking vehicles, pedestrians, and objects.
- **Performance Indicator:** The end-to-end detection latency, i.e., the time a frame takes from acquisition to detection, **shall achieve a minimum frame rate of 20 Frames Per Second (FPS) for each camera.** The system's ability to assess speed in object identification and tracking must consistently meet or exceed this specified threshold under various operational conditions and environmental scenarios.
- Rationale: This requirement is fundamental to ensure the system's real-time performance in identifying and tracking objects within its operational domain.

2.4.1.3 **KPI-3: Hardware power consumption**

- Objective: The proposed hardware for the smart city use-case shall undergo a comprehensive evaluation to assess its overall power consumption.
- **Performance Indicator:** The hardware shall achieve a power consumption level **below 20 Watts in the worst-case scenario.** The system's hardware components' efficiency must consistently meet or exceed this specified threshold under diverse operational conditions and environmental scenarios.
- Rationale: This requirement is important to ensure the reliability and efficiency of the hardware components within this use case. The specified power consumption metric provides a quantifiable benchmark for assessing the overall performance of the hardware.
- Non-functional requirement: The HAura system must be powered by a 220V source. Additionally, it requires a reliable internet connection, achievable through various network infrastructures, including Wi-Fi, Ethernet, or SIM card interfaces.

2.4.2. Validation process

To validate KPI-1 and KPI-2 Hipert will provide a synthetic dataset where the consortium will be able to assess the accuracy and timing capabilities. After the assessment on the synthetic dataset, Hipert will evaluate the final performance using the devices featuring the partners' contributions that are deployed in the city. Furthermore, the consortium will assess the system's responses to varying environmental factors, object complexities, and different traffic scenarios will be observed and analysed.

To validate KPI-3, Hipert will perform different power consumption measurements tests will be performed under various stress scenarios to validate the system's stability and reliability.

2.5. Planned partners contributions

In this use case, partners contribute with technologies developed within the project to enhance the performance and expand the current functionalities of the HAura system. Additionally, another group of partners will focus on refining the edge technologies deployed at the vehicle level as a secondary aspect of this collaborative effort. The planned contributions from the partners are depicted in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Distribution of work and work areas among partners

As shown in the figure, the work is divided into two main areas. In particular, the work planned is as follows:

Contributions focused on edge technologies at smart-city level (Hipert, UNIMORE, DFKI, FRAUNHOFER, INSAIT, UCLM):

Hipert will provide HAura as the baseline system for the use case. Furthermore, Hipert will share the output of the system, i.e., the metadata, as the system's output. Additionally, the company will offer support for integrating the technologies developed by the partners in terms of hardware and software and it will strive to provide development/evaluation units to the partners.

UNIMORE will take care of providing access to the MASA infrastructure, identifying a strategic mounting position to install at least one HAura, and coordinating access to the infrastructure. Moreover, UNIMORE will potentially contribute with continual-learning capabilities to improve the precision over time. Also, models and algorithms for parking space detection could be deployed on edge nodes with camera input.

UCLM will develop and test implementations of an automatic weapon detector for surveillance images. The envisaged scenario is surveillance cameras installed at the entrances of a public building, immediately detecting when a lone gunman enters the building (and alerting security staff). Unfortunately, this scenario has become all too common in our society, not only in countries such as USA but also here in Europe (an example is the 2023 Prague mass shooting). The developed system is based on DNNs that consider the weapon appearance but may also consider contextual cues such as body pose. Other sensor types will be considered (thermal camera for concealed weapon detection, PTZ cameras, etc.). Implementations will run on embedded PCs and embedded NVIDIA hardware. The HAura platform will be evaluated as the computation node for performing the detection.

FRAUNHOFER will create an event-camera dataset from a camera mounted on a high-speed train with the aim of inspecting rail adjacent infrastructure. The possibility of processing the event-camera data using sparse CNN methods on the HAura platform will be evaluated. This involves deploying neural networks on the system.

DFKI will develop a deep learning algorithm for detection (and optionally orientation estimation and tracking) of road users for video protection. Moreover, DFKI will potentially contribute on continual learning on the edge. The provided solution is a hybrid solution that will be trained on traditional GPUs but deployed as energy-efficient, real-time FPGA SoC-based implementation. Specifically, the algorithm would be quantized and implemented on Xilinx XCZU9EG SoC chip.

INSAIT: INSAIT will support the smart city use case by focusing on Multi-Task Learning implementations on the Hipert hardware, following guidelines and assistance provided by the University of Modena. Tasks to be considered include the detection of multiple traffic agents.

FORTH, as T5.3 leader, will provide porting guidance to the use case to adopt parts of hardware technologies developed at T5.3. Forth will select a suitable hardware platform out of those that T5.3 develops and use it to integrate parts of the use case and collect measurements.

BTH, could potentially work with a 'cloned use case' built with similar / identical artefacts where security & privacy-preserving performance will be considered as a parameter for measuring, validating, and improving the cyber-security of the smart city use case. BTH's objectives include but are not limited to the following:

- To investigate the feasibility of adopting PETs within the use case, e.g., homomorphic encryption, differential privacy, federated learning, etc.
- To investigate the feasibility of attaining transparency within the use case, e.g., explainability, interpretability, etc.
- To assess the trade-off for adopting privacy and security by design approaches within a smart city scenario.
- To assess compliance with the regulatory aspects and potential infringements, e.g., EU AI Act.

Hence, research and development efforts could be carried out in a parallel manner, while BTH would focus on sustainability through the above-mentioned aspects concerning security and privacy of smart city residents. We also envision a KPI validation study, which would shed light on trade-offs, granular controls, informed decisions, etc.

Contributions focused on edge technologies at vehicle level (Aegis Rider, VERSES, CSEM):

Aegis Rider will contribute by deploying its augmented reality motorcycle helmet (see Figure 7) with neural accelerator, using Qualcomm QCS6490 chipset. The device has WiFi/BT connectivity interfaces. Hazardous objects detected by HAura will be transmitted and visualized by the motorcyclist in AR. This includes real-time pedestrian and vehicle geo-locations, with these agents being visually "highlighted" using the Aegis Rider augmented reality system. Aegis Rider will develop and evaluate different visualization techniques to ensure fast and effective communication with the

rider. Communication between the HAura and the Aegis Rider helmet will be developed, with a focus on low latency and robustness. Optionally, Aegis Rider will evaluate the deployment of the Hipert HAura system on the motorcycle itself to enable real time Advanced Rider Assistance Systems (ARAS). Aegis Rider will perform the interface integration based on Hipert's API.

Figure 7. Aegis Rider helmet featuring VR technology

Aegis Rider will also assess the integration of an eye-tracking camera system to work with CSEM algorithms developed for efficient real time facial feature extraction to enable rider state monitoring (alertness, drowsiness, etc.) and 3D gaze estimation to understand if a rider has seen a potentially hazardous agent. As an eye-tracking system is currently not part of the Aegis Rider helmet, appropriate hardware needs to be found and evaluated in terms of fit into the helmet and performance with different user facial dimensions.

CSEM will contribute with its mixed physics-based machine learning algorithm pipeline for real time facial feature extraction. These mixed pipelines allow efficient physics-based methods when possible, reducing the power consumption and time to execute the algorithms. The eye gaze tracking algorithms developed at CSEM can consider personal on-line calibration for higher accuracy. Different feature extractions are possible such as eye gaze, perclos (eye distance between the eyelids), yawning, head position etc. These algorithms will need to be modified to assess if they can work on helmets.

VERSES will evaluate the fitness of the open standards and specifications, specifically Hyperspace Modelling Language (HSML) and Hyperspace Transaction Protocol (HSTP), as well as the Active Inference framework to the use case:

- **Hyperspace Modelling Language (HSML)**

A human and machine-readable language for normalizing and contextualizing heterogeneous data by restructuring them in an ontological model that reflects their spatial and semantic interrelationships and interdependencies.

- **Hyperspace Transaction Protocol (HSTP)**

A multi-dimensional query protocol for monitoring real-world assets and mediating views of, and updates to, their corresponding digital record (i.e., digital twin), based on activities, permissions, and policies.

- **Active Inference Framework**

This theoretical framework can be applied to a variety of domains, including robotics, artificial intelligence, and the Internet of Things (IoT). It is based on the principle that agents – which can be biological organisms or artificial systems – infer the state of the world and themselves through a process of minimizing their surprise or prediction error about sensory inputs. In the context of IoT, it can enable devices to adaptively communicate and become context-aware, among other things. It allows devices to predict and adapt to the data formats and communication protocols of other devices dynamically and adjust their operations to the current environmental conditions and the states of other devices.

3. AI on the edge for satellite

The space use case considers the task of data processing on an Earth Observation satellite. Currently, data is mostly downlinked to a ground station before processing, but this is changing with new generations of satellites, bringing the processing onboard to reduce latency. In a sense, space is the ultimate Edge AI scenario. More detail is presented in the following sections on background and use case description, followed by the technical specifications, the validation plan and the partners' contributions.

3.1. Background

This section gives a very brief overview of the terms and technologies dealt with in the Space use case, with a focus on their relevance for the dAIEdge project. It is not within the scope of the document to give a full overview of all the topics, for this, the reader is referred to literature.

3.1.1. Satellite Earth Observation

Earth Observation (EO) monitors Earth from a distance, which in principle can be airplanes, balloons, high altitude platforms, or, first and foremost, satellites. Its task is to retrieve information on the processes on the ground or within the atmosphere. Most EO satellites are positioned in the Lower Earth Orbit (LEO) at about 500-800 km altitude, however, there are also geostationary satellites (~36000 km altitude), e.g. the MeteoSATs for large-scale weather monitoring. Their orbit is often polar, so their course over ground passes close to the North- and South pole. Since the Earth is rotating below, they can cover the full globe over the course of several orbits.

In the current state-of-the-art, acquired raw data is stored in the satellite until it establishes contact with a ground station. Then the data is downlinked to the ground for further processing, usually on large servers. Depending on the satellite travel time and processing demands, this can take up to 30 min when a Near-real time (NRT) processing chain is set up. The goal of this demonstrator is to show that this time can be greatly reduced by conducting the processing on the edge, aboard the satellite, and the up-to-date AI inference tasks are possible on such a system.

3.1.2. Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR)

EO satellites can be grouped into two categories: active and passive. Passive satellites are for example optical satellites, basically cameras in space, measuring the sunlight reflected back from

the ground. Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) sensors belong to the active category. They have an active microwave antenna to send radar signals towards the ground and receive their reflected echo. Their advantage compared to optical acquisitions is that SAR penetrates clouds and is not dependent on sunlight. Both are very important features for operational use in safety and security applications, where reliable acquisitions are required.

The electromagnetic waves transmitted by SAR always have a certain orientation (perpendicular to the main beam direction) with respect to the ground, these are called polarizations. Horizontal and vertical polarizations are most common, but also circular polarizations are available from some sensors. When receiving, the antenna can also discriminate the polarizations. Hence, polarization is given as <Sent><Received>, for example an image has HH polarization if the antenna was set to transmit and receive horizontally. A single pol acquisition is the simplest setup, often with the highest resolution. ESA's Sentinel-1 satellites offer HH/HV or VV/VH acquisitions, which means both polarizations are available as individual images. From other sensors, it is possible to get full polarization scenes with HH/VV/HV/VH; more options may exist where circular polarizations are offered. When multiple polarizations exist, they are often shown in previews as different RGB channels of the image, giving the SAR scenes a coloured appearance (see Figure 7). The reason for using multiple polarizations is that different surface types scatter polarizations differently. Hence, having multiple polarizations available can strongly increase the accuracy of surface classifications.

Figure 7: Example for SAR acquisitions by Sentinel-1 (EW GRDM mode, HH/HV polarizations, 400 km swath width, 40 m pixel spacing), left: coarse preview image with polarizations mapped to different colour channels, right: zoom-in of full HH image, showing larger and smaller ice floes (upper parts) and land (lower parts). The size of the full scene is approximately 10.000 x 10.000 pixels.

3.1.3. SAR data processing

The data produced by the SAR sensor (LO data) are unintelligible for a human viewer until they run through the process of image formation. This uses multiple mathematical operations (e.g., FFTs) to

focus the data in azimuth and range direction, forming the SAR image (L1 data). Azimuth and range are the two dimensions of a SAR image. Range refers to the across-track (perpendicular to the flight direction), while azimuth refers to the along-track (parallel to the flight direction). This L1 image looks very similar to spaceborne optical data and can easily be interpreted by the human eye (and AIs). However, it is grayscale, since it depicts the SAR backscatter signal intensity, which correlates with the surface roughness. For example, ships at sea can be easily spotted as bright dots, since their metal structures are excellent radar reflectors compared to the surrounding water. On the other hand, oil spills are so smooth that they reflect all SAR radiation away from the sensor and appear darker than the surrounding ocean, where some backscatter is caused by ocean waves. Extraction of such information (ships, oil, sea ice, etc.) is called value-adding and value-added products are referred to as L2-data.

Figure 8: Example of SAR RAW data (left) and focused data (right; top is water, bottom is land)

3.1.4. Sea ice

Sea ice is ice created by freezing sea water (in contrast to freezing freshwater on land, e.g. glacier ice). It is a common occurrence in oceans in polar latitudes, such as the northern Baltic Sea, the north-eastern Atlantic or the waters around Antarctica. It is present year-round in the coldest areas and seasonal (in winter) in less cold areas. It occurs in different thicknesses often distinguished by age (young ice, first year ice, multi-year ice); older ice usually has a higher thickness. Sea ice often forms ice floes, larger regions of ice which stick together, either frozen together with other floes or drifting freely through mostly open water (note that drifting flows are not icebergs, which are formed by glacier break-offs). Sea ice is often also covered by snow.

For marine traffic, sea ice is a threat since the hard and thick flows can severely damage a ship's hull. Some situations, such as ice floes drifting together and forming so-called pressure ridges, can even be dangerous and impassable for icebreakers. Most commercial ships aim to avoid ice-covered waters, in other situations an icebreaker will lead a convoy consisting of ships with lower ice class (ability to sail through ice).

Many ships crossing polar latitudes are equipped with an ice radar, scanning and displaying the sea ice situation in a radius of about 20 km around the ship. Satellite acquisitions of the sea ice situation can provide a good long-distance view for navigation, allowing to find the safest and fastest route through the ice. This is used, for example, by the German research vessel Polarstern, for which DLR provides images from its TerraSAR-X radar satellite during polar campaigns. Since the sea ice is drifting (mostly caused by wind), the sea ice situation is constantly changing, so very recent data is required for safe navigation.

3.1.5. Sea ice classification from SAR images

As explained earlier, a SAR image shows surface roughness by different brightness of the pixels. In the case of sea ice, this roughness often correlates with the age and thickness of sea ice. Hence, it is often classified by age, such as young ice, first year ice or multi-year ice. Also, it needs to be discriminated from open water and land. A land mask is often used for land filtering, but it could also be included as part of the AI training.

The output of a classification is an image with the same coverage, but the pixel resolution might be reduced (depending on the chosen classification method) and all pixels flagged with a numerical value belonging to an ice class. Other representations are possible as well. Additionally, boundaries between different classes can be extracted as polygons.

Many standard approaches to image classification can be applied to L1 SAR data, and most approaches for regular images will work for SAR data as well.

3.1.6. Autonomous observation

Modern Earth Observation Satellites have three degrees of freedom and can observe the full visible time window onto ground targets. The imaging time of the satellite observing a ground target is fixed and preset. The earth observation scheduling problem consists in selecting a set of feasible observations to perform automatically. The basic problem has been proved to be NP-hard in Lemaitre's work (Le maître & all (2002)) where fixed and constant image duration for each task is assumed. The operational gain of such an approach has been demonstrated by real systems such as Earth – Observer One (EO1) in the 2005-2015 period. However, the problem can be generalized to spacecraft constellations (Gauthier et al., 2022; Parjan and Chien, 2023). In further works, agencies and operators envisage a Multi Agent System Approach (MAS) to model the main problem as a decentralized scheduling solution. Decentralized scheduling addresses both the system's robustness and the vulnerabilities of a central controller. This approach is becoming very interesting thanks to intersatellite links. We propose two scenarios with two levels of difficulty, extending the SAR capabilities to autonomous observations. They can be addressed by consortium members or third parties.

3.1.7. Further reading

- Publication describing the implementation of SAR image formation and SAR value adding on an MPSoC system (ARM CPU + FPGA): <https://elib.dlr.de/187505/>

- Publication describing the results from an AI model for sea ice mapping from SAR imagery competition:
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/376448472_The_AutoICE_Challenge
- The website <https://www.meereisportal.de/en> provides lots of information on sea ice
- The Marine SAR User's Manual <https://www.sarusersmanual.com/> offers in-depth knowledge of SAR and its maritime applications

3.2. Use case description

In this Space use case of dAIEdge, we will (1) implement the SAR image formation (L0 to L1 data), as this is how data is made available by the sensor, (2) implement sea ice detection based on the focused images (L1 data), and (3) investigate a direct classification from L0 to L2 data. Additionally, we will investigate possibilities for evaluating the necessity of downlinking the data (e.g. this may be deemed unnecessary in case of no detections) and a refinement/improvement of an initial onboard classification by hardware on the ground after downlink. We will also investigate two scenarios for autonomous observations.

While the implementation will cover all necessary parts of the chain, it will not result in one monolithic demonstration system. Instead, the individual parts will be implemented as stand-alone modules, able to be evaluated against each other and traditional (non-edge hardware) approaches. An overview is provided in Figure 9 and Figure 10.

Figure 9: Workflow of the space use case, part 1. Starting from SAR RAW data, an image formation implementation will be developed. Multiple approaches on different types of hardware will be used for sea ice classification from L1 data. Direct or hybrid classification from L2 data will also be investigated. Only the parts in blue will be implemented in the project.

Figure 10: Workflow of the space use case, part 2. From the L2 classifications, it will be evaluated if the product is worth to be directly downlinked. Also, it is assessed if an on-ground refinement of the onboard classification is beneficial. Only the parts in blue will be implemented in the project.

3.2.1. Image formation

Since the use case is meant to demonstrate all steps of a data processing chain which would be implemented on a satellite, it needs to start with image formation, using the raw data as they are generated by the sensor.

It is expected that image formation does not require the use of AI. The processing is traditionally done with data processing methods such as FFTs and it is known that these deliver the best possible output from the sensor data. Several different SAR image formation algorithms exist and implementations of some of them were demonstrated to run on FPGAs in the past. With sufficient resources (well within the scope available on satellites), a near-real time processing can be achieved, meaning that the image formation is still slower than the satellite acquires new data. The use of AI can, however, be considered for very low performance systems where these algorithms would cause too high latency.

In the use case, we plan to have one implementation of image formation, to be developed by DLR employing an FPGA.

3.2.2. Sea ice classification

Sea ice classification requires the use of AI. In this use case, three different classifiers will be developed and implemented for classification of L1 SAR images. The AI model to be used in each implementation will be determined by the respective partner, keeping in mind the requirements of the edge scenario and, where possible, also the findings of WP5.

3.2.3. Direct classification

In addition, we plan to investigate the benefits of the application of AI in the end-to-end processing chain of SAR data from L0 to feature extraction, either for certain elements in the focusing or the processing chain (producing hybrid pipelines consisting of a mixture of classical and AI algorithms) or by directly applying a feature extraction AI pipeline to the L0 data. This work is to be performed by Ubotica.

3.2.4. Downlink evaluation

With currently operation large EO satellites, all data acquired are planned to be downlinked. Using large fleets of small satellites, it is increasingly likely that there is no interest in data that does not show certain features, e.g. detected sea ice. We will investigate how and to what extent this can be implemented.

3.2.5. Refinement assessment

AI-based data processing on an edge system is a compromise between use of computational resources and AI model performance. While AI models running on ground systems with much more resources and power available will outperform the AI models running on the edge, it might be beneficial to use edge-generated model input as a basis for ground processing. This will also be investigated as part of the use case, e.g. to improve on-ground runtime and/or model performance.

3.2.6. Autonomous observations at the Edge

3.2.6.1 Single spacecraft scheduling observation problem

In this first scenario, the problem focuses on a single satellite with imaging capabilities, orbiting in LEO. We consider a set of observation opportunities for this satellite, obtained by pre-processing tools ephemeris, to observe an area of interest. We consider that observation opportunities are candidate to be selected or not as part of an observation plan, which is the solution to the problem.

Figure 11: Sketch of observation and downlink opportunities for Earth Observation satellites.

A generic user story can be considered as follows for the single spacecraft scheduling observation problem:

Figure 12: User story for single spacecraft scenario

Preparations and Operational phases are sequential. Once observations are optimized, the satellites perform sequentially all selected observations.

For each observation opportunity, we consider:

- An observation temporal window (earliest and latest start time)
- Duration (strictly positive)

We also consider a list of observation demands (area of interest location) where multiple criteria can apply:

- Quality (azimuth)
- Deadline (strict or soft constraint)

The goal is to fulfil the maximum number of observation demands, according to above criteria, in a receding arbitrary time horizon. The following operational constraints need to be satisfied:

- Each observation demand is performed at most once
- Whenever an observation is activated, it fulfils its temporal window
- The satellite activates observations sequentially, with minimum path footprint of the area of interest
- The satellite can perform a single observation at a given time (no simultaneous observations)
- The satellite stays on a fixed orbital plane and elliptic kinematics.

For each candidate, the planner needs to decide whether the opportunity is activated. A formal model example is available in Le maître & al (2002).

3.2.6.2 Multiple spacecraft scheduling observation problem, with distributed task allocation

To extend the problem, this second scenario considers multiple satellites, spread on several orbital planes. Each satellite stays on a fixed plane and ellipse.

Additional operational constraints are the following:

- No two spacecraft fulfil the same request. Alternatively, this can be difficult to achieve depending on the solving approach, in the case of distributed solving. This can be modelled either as hard constraint, or as cost function.
- Each spacecraft has a limited memory capability, and can download observation data on a specific time window (ground station visibility)
- The information bandwidth between the satellites might be constrained in multiple ways:
 - Low speed link between spacecrafts, but high-speed link on specific time window with earth.
 - Transient link quality

In this scenario, we also consider re-planning capabilities due to two contingent events:

- The platform needs to switch to AOCS modes, which temporarily disables observation capabilities.
- The observation in area of interest is not observable due to meteorological conditions.

Optionally, solving might be distributed in embedded satellite computing capabilities.

A generic user story can be considered as follows for the multiple spacecraft scheduling observation problem, with distributed allocation task:

Figure 13: User story for multi-spacecraft scenario

Here, the multiple satellites use case is generalized by reusing its ground preparation and space operational phases in the life cycle of the constellation. The distributed optimization is highly important to maximize efficiency of constellation. More details can be found in the following publications: Gauthier et al. (2022) and Parjan & Chien (2023).

3.3. Technical specification

This section provides information on the hard- and software to be used in this use case.

3.3.1. Hardware description

This use case will employ different hardware provided by different partners. Computational hardware to be used on an actual satellite has strict requirements, for example with respect to radiation hardening. Therefore, depending on the partners’ decisions and capabilities, the hardware used may not be space-certified, but comparable to available space-certified systems.

3.3.1.1 Xilinx Zynq UltraScale+ MPSoC System

Zynq UltraScale+ MPSoC is a highly advanced system-on-chip (SoC) developed by Xilinx. It integrates a multi-core processing system (PS), consisting of an ARM Cortex-A53 based APU and Cortex-R5 based RPU, along with the programmability of an FPGA also called programmable logic (PL) in a single chip. This heterogeneous multiprocessing architecture allows for an efficient utilization of resources and enables the development of complex and sophisticated applications. The MPSoC also offers a rich set of peripherals and interfaces, including high-speed serial transceivers, Ethernet, USB, and PCIe, which facilitate seamless connectivity with external devices and systems. The block diagram of Zynq UltraScale+ MPSoC is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Block Diagram of Zynq UltraScale+ MPSoC

The largest device offered in the Zynq UltraScale+ MPSoC family is the ZU19EG. This chip is available on a plug-in daughter board for the proFPGA Uno prototyping mainboard (Figure 15). The proFPGA mainboard provides up to 8 extension sites, allowing to add additional functionality or connect daughter boards for specific applications. The current setup includes one proFPGA DDR4-5GB SDRAM daughter board and one proFPGA Gigabit Ethernet interface board.

Figure 15: proFPGA Uno prototyping board with Xilinx Zynq UltraScale+ ZU19EG MPSoC

Xilinx ZCU102 Evaluation Board is also chosen for the implementation of this use case. Zynq® UltraScale+™ XCZU9EG-2FFVB1156E MPSoC is the core of this general-purpose platform. In this platform, the PS is a multiprocessor System-on-Chip consisting of an ARM® flagship Cortex®-A53 64-bit quad-core processor and a Cortex-R5 dual-core real-time processor along with high speed DDR4 SODIMM and component memory interfaces. The PL is basically the Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) which features 912 (Block RAM) BRAMs, 2520 DSP48, 274k (Look-Up Tables) LUTs and 548k (Flip-Flops) kFFs. Figure 16 shows an overview of the board and its components.

Figure 16: ZCU evaluation board with Xilinx Zynq UltraScale+ XCZU9EG MPSoC

3.3.1.2 Intel Movidius Myriad X Vision Processing Unit

Myriad X builds on the capabilities of the 28nm Myriad 2 combining additional proprietary programmable SHAVE cores with fixed-function vision accelerators implemented in 16nm FinFet technology from TSMC. Myriad X adds the Neural Compute Engine (NCE), boosting the design’s compute power to one trillion operations per second (fp16 TOPS) when combining the NCE and the SHAVE cores. It also adds video and crypto accelerators to increase application performance and dissipates from 1-2.5W depending on the application. This Myriad X VPU is the central processor of the CogniSat-XE2 processing board.

Figure 17: MyriadX Block Diagram [“Myriad X press release”, Aug 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://newsroom.intel.com/news/intel-unveils-neural-compute-engine-movidius-myriad-x-vpu-unleash-ai-edge/>]

The CogniSat-XE2 processing board is a designed-for-space COTS board. The Myriad X device contains 16 128-bit vector processing cores that provide high-performance parallel compute, and additionally has hardware acceleration for common vision and AI tasks, all within a low power

envelope of 2-3.5W. Due to its inherent flexibility as a software controlled software-hardware platform, the Myriad X can support a wide range of NN architectures compiled via the OpenVINO toolchain, and supports models from common frameworks such as PyTorch, TensorFlow, Keras and ONNX. The Myriad X, and the XE2 board, have recently undergone extensive radiation testing under a current ESA programme, with results indicating suitability for LEO operations. Myriad X has previously flown on the ISS, successfully demonstrating AI inference over the course of 18 months for a range of AI models, and on the D-Orbit Wild Ride mission in 2021. Furthermore, the predecessor Myriad device – the Myriad 2 - has flight heritage on PhiSat-1 (2020) and more recently on the Platero and MANTIS CubeSat missions from Open Cosmos (2023).

Figure 18: CogniSAT-XE2 space-grade AI co-processing board

The CogniSAT-XE2 PC104 form factor AI co-processing board, shown in Figure a, includes interfaces for integration into SmallSat architectures, and is supported by Computer Vision/AI control software that enables running multiple applications in parallel on the Myriad X VPU in the system. CogniSAT-XE2 boards are built in conformance with IPC class 3 standards and designed according to the ESA TEC-ED specification for CubeSat processing boards. Multiple XE platform design features provide robustness for operations in LEO, including use of automotive components and components with prior testing or flight heritage, full custom on-board latch-up protection, a custom power distribution network optimised for efficiency and excluding the use of LDOs, and built-in self-tests. CogniSAT-XE2 will achieve multiple flight heritage in early Q1 2024.

3.3.2. Software description

This section describes the software and data to be used in the space use case.

3.3.2.1 AI Sea Ice Classifiers

This use case will implement different classifiers, which will in the end allow a comparison between them. While the partners have experience with classifying images and/or SAR data, the actual classifiers to be used and to be implemented in hardware do not yet exist. Their development and suitable design for the hardware used, also considering the findings and guidelines from other parts of the project (especially WP5), are a core part of this use case.

3.3.2.2 Dataset

Different sea ice classifiers will be developed during this use case, using different algorithms and running on different hardware. To achieve comparable results between those algorithms, the same dataset should be used by all of them.

The dataset to be used in this use case is the “AI4Arctic / ASIP Sea Ice Dataset - version 3”, found here: https://data.dtu.dk/collections/AI4Arctic_Sea_Ice_Challenge_Dataset/6244065 (accessed 2024-01-11); the download sited to the datasets (posted on 2023-02-14) are:

RAW:

https://data.dtu.dk/articles/dataset/Raw_AI4Arctic_Sea_Ice_Challenge_Dataset/21284967?backTo=/collections/AI4Arctic_Sea_Ice_Challenge_Dataset/6244065

Ready-to-use: https://data.dtu.dk/articles/dataset/Ready-To-Train_AI4Arctic_Sea_Ice_Challenge_Dataset/21316608?backTo=/collections/AI4Arctic_Sea_Ice_Challenge_Dataset/6244065

Within the dataset, “raw” data refers to not pre-processed Sentinel-1 data, while “ready-to-use” data is pre-processed and downsampled from 40m pixel spacing to 80m.

The dataset consists of 513 Sentinel-1 EW scenes acquired around Greenland. These were collected by DTU and collocated with ice charts created by DMI. It also has additional data by AMSR2 (a microwave sensor on a different satellite), which is not to become part of the use case – data fusion from products from a fully different satellite is not meaningful in terms of near real-time data generation and onboard processing. Hence, only the S1 data is to be used.

In addition to the files provided in this dataset, the corresponding Sentinel-1 RAW data can be used, which is not part of the dataset and needs to be downloaded from, e.g., the Copernicus Dataspace (<https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/>).

3.4. Validation plan

3.4.1. KPIs

The key performance indicators (KPIs) will be used to quantitatively compare different implementations of the sea ice classification algorithms and the different hardware these are running on. Target numbers are provided to illustrate the approximate order of magnitude foreseen

in the implementations, however due to the new and experimental nature of the task, trade-offs may have to be made.

The following KPIs have been identified in this use case:

3.4.1.1 KPI 1: Latency [s]

For fast processing in space, a low latency (processing time) is essential. If the time was to become too high, the data may instead be downlinked to the ground and processed there. The measurement of latency must include the full processing, starting with the input data in memory, running the actual sea ice classification inference for the full scene, and writing the classified output image to memory or storage.

A processing latency in the order of 1 minute is envisaged.

3.4.1.2 KPI 2: Power consumption [W]

For determining the suitability of a system to be useable in space, power consumption is a crucial factor. Lower power consumption enables the use of a system on smaller satellites with high constraints to battery and power grids, while larger satellites can easily handle higher power demands and allow higher processing performance.

For this use case, a maximum consumption of 30 W during 1 minute of processing is envisaged.

3.4.1.3 KPI 3: Memory consumption [GB]

Algorithms need varied amount of RAM while running, and in edge devices the amount of memory could be rather limited. Hence, an algorithm which can adapt itself to the RAM space available is advantageous.

The RAM needs should not exceed what is available on the hardware used, staying below 16 GB is envisaged.

3.4.1.4 KPI 4: Classification accuracy [F1 score]

This refers to accuracy in detecting target classes e.g. different sea ice classes and water. The F1 score will be used as classification accuracy metric. If relevant, we can also consider the uncertainty measure from the algorithm. Ideally, the algorithm should provide information about the prediction confidence.

The developed classifiers should aim for an F1 score above 0.8.

3.4.1.5 KPI 5: Classification resolution [m]

The Sentinel-1 EW data used has an original resolution of 25 m (GRDH scenes) or 40 m (GRDM scenes), 40 m are provided in the raw dataset (see section 3.3.2.2). A developed classification may end up providing a strongly reduced resolution only. Since the training dataset uses coarse sea charts, a classification may reach good scores in KPI 3 at the expense of resolution, reducing the usefulness of the classification for tactical navigation.

The developed classifiers should have a classification resolution better than 200 m.

3.4.2. Requirements

This table defines functional requirements for the individual classifiers developed.

R1	The classifier must apply machine learning / artificial intelligence
R2	Only the dataset(s) described in 3.3.2.2 of this document must be used for training, testing and validation.
R3	The inference of the classifier must fully run on hardware specified in Section 3.3.1 of this document
R4	The performance measure for inference (KPI1) must fully run on hardware specified in Section 3.3.1 of this document.

3.5. Planned partner contributions

As described before, this use case handles the case of data processing on board of an Earth Observation satellite, using the task of sea ice classification from SAR data as the demonstration case. The tasks cover different steps of the processing chain and are split between multiple partners. By the design of the use case, their work is performed mostly independently, allowing also highly experimental approaches. In case of the L1->L2 classification, multiple implementations will be developed by the partners for the same task and can later be compared.

DLR is in lead of this use case. They will develop a SAR image formation stage (L0->L1, Task 3.2.1) and a sea ice classification from the L1 SAR image (Task 3.2.2). Both will be implemented on the MPSoC/FPGA system described in Section 3.3.1.

DFKI will develop a deep learning algorithm for sea ice classification of L1 images (Task 3.2.2). Eventually, the algorithm would be quantized and implemented on a Xilinx XZCU9EG SoC chip.

SED will investigate two scenarios for Autonomous Observation at the Edge (Task 3.2.6).

Ubotica will perform the compilation and benchmarking of developed AI algorithms on the CogniSat-XE2 board (Task 3.2.2) and will investigate the benefits of the application of AI in (parts of) the end-to-end SAR processing chain from L0 (Task 3.2.3).

VICOM will work on classification algorithms (Task 3.2.2) and monitoring the performance of edge classification algorithms against algorithms running on the ground (on-premise or cloud) and refining the classification assessment of edge algorithms with on-ground results (Tasks 3.2.4 and 3.2.5).

FORTH, as T5.3 leader, will provide porting guidance to the use case to adopt parts of hardware technologies developed at T5.3.

4. Drone Assisted Warehouse

4.1. Background

Modern warehouses are hubs of activity and cutting-edge technology, where AGVs (Automated Guided Vehicles), AMRs (Autonomous Mobile Robots), and UAVs (Unmanned Aerial Vehicles) thrive in harmony. Amidst high levels of automation, workers operate machinery and check inventory manually. The primary issues in managing warehouses include handling inventory, arranging products, and ensuring precise order picking. This particular use case tackles these challenges through the implementation of drone monitoring and inspection. Autonomous drones will be utilised to survey the warehouse's exterior to maintain security. Internally, these drones will be tested for conducting inspections on racks and tracking assets. Additionally, we will attempt to demonstrate coordination between human activity and robot activity using AMRs.

Managing the activities of the robots/drones is the Genius™ platform and agents that oversee and coordinate all the different robots in the warehouse. Genius™ taps into a vast knowledge database, gathering real-time data to make informed decisions and efficiently delegate tasks.

4.2. Use Case Description

4.2.1. Description

We aim to solve warehouse challenges using a drone for monitoring and inspection. An autonomous drone will monitor the warehouse perimeter for security and inspect racks and assets inside. Information collected by the drone will be shown in a digital twin of the warehouse, possibly accessible via screens or Head-Mounted Displays (HMDs) for workers.

External monitoring first detects intruders or irregular activity. When security cameras detect movement, a drone are automatically deployed. Genius™ displays drone activity and live camera feeds, allowing administrators and authorized workers to track and communicate with potential intruders (e.g., using drone speakers and lights if mounted on the drone).

Inside the warehouse, the drone inspects racks and track assets, updating a warehouse digital twin. Drones and AMRs are routed for efficient movement, minimizing worker travel time and congestion in busy areas.

Collaboration between human workers and AMRs addresses challenges in order picking and delivery. VICOM will explore coexistence and collaboration levels between humans and AMRs, ensuring safe working environments for tasks like placing products on racks or shared tasks where robots pick and deliver products. AI integrated with AMRs could therefore support collaboration and enable digital twins for both human workers and robots in the warehouse.

4.2.2. Scope Of Work

The objective of this use case is to enhance warehouse services, such that we attain a hyper-connected and smart environment with the following capabilities:

- **Path Planning**

This involves the mapping of routes and pathways, ensuring efficient navigation for various entities like robots. It focuses on determining the optimal paths to reach destinations while considering obstacles and constraints.

- **Advanced Routing**

Determining the best paths for agents (i.e., robots and drones) to follow. Re-routing also requires the ability to adjust the directions in response to real-time conditions and unexpected changes in the setting.

- **Agent-Agnostic Communication and Coordination**

Focuses on establishing communication and collaboration among different agents, regardless of their specific functionalities, aiming at seamless interaction and cooperation. This enhances the outcomes of WP7 that aim for a collaborative agent environment – HSML (Hyperspace Modelling Language), as a protocol, helps modelling space for autonomous agents, facilitating efficient sharing of intelligence.

- **Contextual Database for Agents**

Involves maintaining a database that stores relevant contextual information essential for agents' decision-making processes. This database provides crucial insights and information, enabling agents to make informed decisions based on context. Genius™ serves as a framework for agents to understand contextualized data, aligning with the primary goal of WP1 in establishing a European AI Lighthouse.

- **Human-Robot Collaboration**

When workers in a warehouse need assistance from robots for specific tasks, such as item picking, transporting etc., robots should be able to perceive the behaviour of the worker and react accordingly, helping to complete those tasks. HRC focuses on enabling robot perception on human behaviours and learning robot control policies on item transporting tasks.

Overall Scope:

This use case aims at demonstrating the system's ability to handle a dynamic, busy environment such as a warehouse:

- Each AMR navigates through the warehouse using its sensors and HSML (Hyperspace Modelling Language), avoiding obstacles and successfully completing tasks.
- Genius™ orchestrates the movements of UAVs and AMRs by utilizing the routing API and its knowledge database. These IoT systems can adapt and re-route autonomously to ensure efficient paths while maintaining safety.
- The system designates specific areas for human activity, ensuring that autonomous systems operate in separate zones.
- Genius™ optimises paths considering real-time data, ensuring the autonomous vehicles steer clear of obstacles to prevent accidents.
- Sensors detect unexpected obstacles, such as fallen boxes, allowing Genius™ to instruct autonomous agents to respond appropriately to maintain safety and productivity.

These capabilities collectively create efficient and adaptable systems where agents can navigate, communicate, and orchestrate movements effectively, ensuring optimized operations within various environments.

4.2.3. Play-by-play

To demonstrate the capabilities of the work carried out across the working packages and validate the technologies, the following scenarios will be implemented:

1. Smart Warehouse Monitoring

- a. A sensor on the outer perimeter of the warehouse is triggered (e.g., proximity sensor or camera)
- b. The camera detects an unidentified individual
- c. The camera sends a command to the drone
- d. Genius™ automatically sets waypoints for the drone to follow, from the take-off area to the triggered sensor
- e. Using advanced routing and live video stream, the UAV flies to destination
- f. The drone hovers over the sensor, locks position and follows the intruder using computer vision
- g. After the security guard secures the perimeter, the drone returns home.

2. Smart Warehouse Routing

- a. An AMR, tasked with moving a box from one end of the warehouse to another, starts its journey. Leveraging the database, the AMR knows where the box needs to go.
- b. The AMR begins its movement, efficiently navigating the environment using data derived from the HSML – a 3D map of the warehouse, constantly updated in real-time.
- c. Shortly after, a box falls off a nearby stack, landing directly in the AMR's planned path. The AMR, equipped with the ability to sense and avoid obstacles, communicates this unexpected hurdle back to Genius™.
- d. Genius™ processes this information and reroutes the AMR through an alternate path that was previously determined as efficient by the routing API.

3. Human-Robot Collaborative Object Transportation

- a. When the AMR arrives at the location to assist the worker, the worker can command the AMR to take actions such as following, pose adjusting etc., by interacting with the AMR via gestures. Then, the AMR loads the heavy item and transports it to the shipment station.
- b. In some cases, completing asset transporting tasks may require a certain level of adaptability to the surroundings. The successful execution often hinges on the collaboration of multiple partners. Partner VICOM will employ mobile manipulators (i.e., AMR mounted with robotic arm) to work closely with human workers, assisting collaboratively on lifting, carrying, and placing the item.

These scenarios align with and integrate the outcomes of WP3 and WP5 (i.e., identifying HW/SW designs, programming environments, edge AI software frameworks, and addressing implementation challenges). Furthermore, they address the aspect of securing AI at the edge by leveraging the socio-technical Spatial Web standards to preserve privacy, build trust, enable security and interoperability.

4.3. Technical Specifications

4.3.1. Hardware Overview

4.3.1.1 Preferred IoT Systems

IOT TYPE	EXAMPLES
UAVs	DJI (Mini, Mavic, M200, M300) Tello Drone Indoor Robotics (Tando) Flyability (Elios 3) Tinamu Labs
AMRs	Locobot Tiago with UR5 Robotiq FT150 force sensor with 3D cameras (Ensenso N35, X30)
Sensors / Cameras	TP Link Tapo C200

4.3.1.2 PREFERRED Human-collaborative Devices

CATEGORY	EXAMPLES
HMDs	Coordination with vehicles, solution as helmet/smart glasses: The Aegis Rider helmet provides a 6-DOF tracking solution for use within vehicles. It then uses binocular AR optics to anchor and visualize content to the user. Alternatively, wireless devices such as tablets.
Support Technologies	5G internet connection in the warehouse Integration of IoT systems into Genius
Communication Protocols	HSTP, HTTPS, and SSH for communication
Positioning and Network Support	GPS, Wi-Fi 2.4GHz, Wi-Fi 5GHz, Ethernet
Security	HTTPS SWIDs (Spatial Web IDs)
Data	Real-time video streams (e.g., 640x480 from HAura's cameras) JSON (category, numeric ID, latitude, longitude, tracking ID, device ID, timestamp)

4.3.2. Software Overview

4.3.2.1 *Genius™ Platform*

Built upon the Spatial Web standards and Active Inference, Genius™ is a cognitive computing system that takes inspiration from the inherent intelligence and adaptability found in natural biological processes. It represents a shift away from traditional artificial intelligence, which typically relies on vast datasets for learning patterns. Instead, Genius™ mimics the innate mechanisms of nature to understand and engage with the world, functioning more like a biological entity than a conventional computer system.

The Spatial Web standards, inherent to Genius™, consist in HSML (Hyperspace Modelling Language) and HSTP (Hyperspace Transaction Protocol). HSML is a data model that facilitates adaptive intelligence on a large scale by modelling spatial and hyperdimensional relationships. HSML encodes properties of physical objects, logical concepts, and contextual activities linking people, places, things and activities. It facilitates multimodal modelling and knowledge sharing among machines and humans. As for HSTP, it is a protocol for querying HSML, it allows for multi-dimensional range queries and governs the secure interactions between parties. HSTP provides a universal, secure, and verifiable protocol for communicating HSML between digital and physical systems. It ensures seamless interaction between diverse AI systems and incorporates a zero-trust architecture for secure data exchange and control over AI operations. These tools are essential for stakeholders to manage identities, activities, spaces, and locations across different data domains, ensuring privacy and security. Recognizing their critical role, IEEE has marked HSML and HSTP as “Public Imperative,” a designation typically reserved for critical public infrastructure like nuclear energy, smart grids, and voting machines.

As for Active Inference, the other building block inherent to Genius™, it is a theoretical framework backed by profound research by Prof. Karl Friston, for understanding how agents, whether they are living organisms or artificial systems, interact with their environment. It posits that these agents are fundamentally engaged in minimizing the difference between their expected sensory inputs and the actual sensory inputs they receive. This is done by making predictions about the world and then acting to make those predictions come true, effectively reducing the uncertainty or “surprise” the agent experiences.

At the core of Genius™ are software entities called *Genius Agents*. These agents are unique in that they empower the user to create and customize their own Genius Agents, tailoring them to their specific needs and challenges. These agents are akin to biological cells in their versatility and are capable of learning, reasoning, planning, and adapting across a variety of contexts.

Genius™ constructs a comprehensive, multi-dimensional representation of the world from diverse data sources, including spatial data like geometry and geography. This “digital brain” allows Genius Agents to make sense of complex dynamics and causality, leading to more accurate predictions and understanding. Genius Agents require minimal data to learn and operate with high computational and energy efficiency. This means that, much like a child learning to recognize a cat or ride a bike with minimal instruction, Genius™ can achieve understanding with a surprisingly sparse amount of data.

Transparency and trust are built into the design of Genius™. It is engineered to be fully transparent and auditable, ensuring data privacy and security with strong identity and credentialing systems. This approach allows for clear tracing of data lineage and decision-making pathways, fostering trust and enabling collaboration. Interoperability and seamless integration across various platforms and systems are also key features of Genius™, as it employs intuitive “world models” that are designed to be understood by both machines and humans alike.

Genius™ embodies distributed intelligence, creating an ecosystem where each part, from sensors to drones to vehicles, and even humans, can collaborate and contribute intelligence to the whole system. This distributed network of Genius Agents can operate both in cloud-based systems and on local devices (the edge), allowing for a scalable and resilient collective intelligence that can self-organize and adapt to changing environments.

4.4. Validation Plan

The validation plan consists in a sequence of assessments aimed at showcasing the improved capabilities and heightened functionalities achieved in a warehouse setting leveraging the Genius platform. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) allow for a correct evaluation and validation of the use case. These are divided into multiple categories to gauge the level of improvement achieved across security monitoring, daily operations, and human-robot collaboration:

- System performance and reliability
- Routing Efficiency
- Energy efficiency and scalability
- Intuitive and interactive virtual 3D environment
- Legal and ethical compliance
- Virtual Environment Interaction and Usability

4.4.1. KPI 1: System Performance and Reliability

- Measure the accuracy of the system in terms of sensitivity (True Positive Rate) and specificity (True Negative Rate). Ensure the monitoring system is operational without malfunctions or downtime
- Measure the time from intrusion detection to drone deployment and eventual resolution
- Track data accuracy in the system and the frequency at which it is updated

4.4.2. KPI 2: Routing efficiency

- Measure the optimization of the overall completion time for tasks through the implementation of accurate and advanced routing strategies employed by UAVs and AMRs. This evaluation includes assessing the precision of routing decisions and their impact.
- Evaluate the impact of advanced routing on reducing workers’ travel time.

- We are targeting up to 10% increase in travel efficiency thanks to improved routing and sequencing of tasks in comparison to manual picking.
- Monitor and aim to reduce congestion in busy areas of the warehouse.

4.4.3. KPI 3: Scalable Energy Efficient Computation

- Ensure lower computational costs on servers and edge devices while maintaining scalability.
- Measure the effectiveness of shared intelligence among multiple agents in the warehouse environment to check that it reduces the computational cost per agent.

4.4.4. KPI 4: Collaborative Human-AI

- Measure the efficiency of human and AMR collaboration in completing tasks.
 - We are targeting up to 10% overall increase in productivity (e.g., tasks and units per hour moved) for collaborative tasks compared to non-collaborative manual picking.
- Survey workers (or users) for their comfort and satisfaction levels working alongside AMRs.
- Explore possibilities of creating an intuitive and interactive virtual 3D environment, as shown in Figure 16, to visualize the warehouse and all the agents.
 - This would allow for fast and easy warehouse worker training and onboarding, as well as effective human-governed AI.

Figure 19: Interactive 3D Model of a Warehouse

4.4.5. KPI 5: Legal and Ethical Compliance

- Ensure GDPR compliance involving data minimization, purpose limitation, and data subject rights.
- Monitor and correct any biases in the algorithm to ensure fairness and prevent discriminatory outcomes.

4.5. Planned Partner Contributions

Our aim is to prove that the convergence of cutting-edge technologies helps overcome common warehouse challenges. Here, each partner contributes to the development and orchestration of an efficient and intelligent ecosystem, enhancing warehouse productivity and streamlining operations:

- **FRAUNHOFER** will evaluate the possibility of AR visualisation of the Digital Twin in worker HMDs. Additionally, we will evaluate the possibility of asset detection from the drone video feed using object detection CNNs.
- **VICOM** will contribute to developing the whole-body control of the mobile manipulator, evaluating the possibility of commanding AMRs via human gestures by integrating human detection, gesture recognition, and robot control. Additionally, VICOM will explore the possibility of learning robot policies for human robot co-transporting from human demonstrations.
- **AEGIS** will provide an augmented reality helmet (HMD) and explore integration possibilities with the Genius™ Platform via Wi-Fi or BT/BLE and receive vital information for the workers. The helmet can be used during vehicle operation (e.g., forklifts). Information is shown via a binocular AR display and can be 2D or 3D. The Aegis Rider helmet allows for the anchoring of content relative to the vehicle. Provided accurate vehicle localization, the Aegis Rider helmet could also show visualize world (warehouse) anchored content such as moving AMRs or drones.
- **USAL** will provide the middleware being developed in parallel in activity 5.2 of the project. The middleware serves as an interconnection system for different actors, enabling authentication and connection with data sets and models developed by various actors in the use cases. This use case can act as a data collection entity, authenticating the origin of the data, and enabling its reuse by other warehouses. The shared models among different actors in the system can include human-robot interaction (HRI), route optimization, and data storage and federation, which will aid in the training of new models.

5. Conclusions

This report marks the initiation of Work Package 6, which encompasses a series of deliverables aimed at defining, implementing, and validating the project's use cases. In this deliverable (D6.1), we have outlined the objectives and scope of the dAIEDGE Project, focusing on three distinct industrial-grade applications within the smart city, space, and logistics domains. This first report serves to gather and delineate the requirements for each application. By establishing a comprehensive set of requirements aligned with the unique demands of each domain, we lay the groundwork for subsequent phases of demonstration, validation, and benchmarking. Furthermore, we have presented a plan outlining the partners' contributions, all of which are aligned with the project's objectives.

Moving forward, the insights gleaned from this initial phase will inform the development and implementation of demonstration setups, validation plans, and ultimately, the execution of the project's objectives. As we progress through the subsequent deliverables, we anticipate further refinement and validation of our approaches, ultimately culminating in the development and integration of innovative edge and fog computing technologies tailored to the specific needs of smart cities, space exploration, and logistics management.

ANNEX A: References

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